

Deliverable D8

Title

Strategy report for offering traceable calibration for testing machines under continuous and dynamic forces

EMPIR Grant Agreement number

18SIB08

Project short name

ComTraForce

Leading partner

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Due date

31.01.2023

Submission date

28.04.2023

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7866831

